

Studies in the Cyclo-octane Series. Part VIII : Synthesis of 2-Alkyl and 2-Aryl-alkyl cyclo-octan-1-ones and of cis-2-Benzyl cyclo-octan-1-ol

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Ethylcyclo-octan-1-one-2-carboxylate is condensed with alkyl/arylalkylchlorides in presence of sodium ethoxide to yield ethyl 2-alkyl/arylalkyl cyclo-octan-1-one-2-carboxylates; hydrolysis and subsequent decarboxylation furnishes the respective 2-substituted cyclo-octan-1-ones. 2-Benzyl cyclo-octan-1-one has been reduced to give cis-2-benzyl cyclo-octan-1-ol.

In continuation of our work on the chemistry of cyclo-octane¹, ethyl cyclo-octan-1-one-2-carboxylate (I) or ethyl cyclo-octan-1-one-2-glyoxalate have been condensed with methyl iodide, ethyl bromide, allyl iodide and benzyl chloride in presence of sodium ethoxide to give the keto-esters of the type (II). These esters on subsequent hydrolysis and decarboxylation furnished the desired ketones (III; R = Me, Et, Allyl or Benzyl) which were characterised through their 2,4-DNPs and semicarbazones. Hydrogenation of III (R = benzyl) could not be effected either at atmospheric pressure or under pressure employing Pd-C, Adams' catalyst or Raney Nickel (W₇). Reduction with sodium borohydride was unsuccessful at low temperature but could be achieved in refluxing ethanol.

On the basis of our earlier work^{3,4,5} and the findings of Dauben *et al.*⁶ and Wheeler *et al.* the alcohol (IV) obtained above is considered to be a cis-isomer. It is believed that the other isomer is not formed at all as shown by TLC. The presence of the hydroxyl group in the reduced product (IV) was confirmed by elemental analysis and I.R. (2.85 μ).

X = COOEt or Co.COOEt.

EXPERIMENTAL

Synthesis of 2-methyl cyclo-octan-1-one (III; R = CH₃).

Method (A): Ethyl cyclo-octan-1-one-2-carboxylate (1.98 g; 0.01 mol) was added to sodium ethoxide (sodium, 0.23 g; 0.01 mol and absolute ethanol, 20 ml) contained in a R.B.

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flask fitted with a double walled reflux condenser carrying a guard tube; the contents were cooled and methyl iodide (3 ml) added with shaking. The reaction mixture, after keeping overnight at room temperature, was refluxed on a water bath until neutral (16 hr.), cooled, poured into water and acidified with dil. hydrochloric acid. The separated oil was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and ether recovered. The residue on distillation gave *pure ethyl 2-methyl cyclo-octa-1-one-2-carboxylate*, b.p. $127^\circ-8^\circ/2$ mm. (Yield : 1.2 g; 57%). (Found : C, 67.8; H, 9.6. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 67.9; H, 9.4%).

The above ester (1 g) was dissolved in alc. potash (potassium hydroxide, 2 g in ethanol, 25 ml and water, 10 ml) and refluxed for 4 hrs. After removing the ethanol, the residue was acidified and the organic material extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and ether recovered; the residue on distillation gave *pure 2-methylcyclo-octa-1-one*, b.p. $71^\circ-3^\circ/4$ mm. (Lit. $74^\circ-5^\circ/7$ mm). (Yield : 0.45 g; 64.3%). n_D^{28} 1.4649. (Found : C, 76.9; H, 11.4. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$ requires C, 77.1; H, 11.4%).

Method (B) : Ethyl cyclo-octan-1-one-2-glyoxalate (2.26 g; 0.01 mol) was added to sodium ethoxide (sodium, 0.23 g; 0.01 mol and absolute ethanol, 20 ml). The mixture cooled and methyl iodide (3 ml) was added with shaking. After keeping overnight at room temperature, the reaction mixture was refluxed until neutral (16 hr), cooled, diluted with water, acidified with dil. hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution on working up in the customary manner gave *pure ethyl 2-methyl cyclo-octa-1-one-2-glyoxalate*, b.p. $109^\circ-110^\circ/0.5$ mm. (Yield : 1.8 g; 66.6%) n_D^{21} 1.4634. (Found : C, 64.9; H, 8.4. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 65.0; H, 8.3%).

The above ester (1.6 g) was refluxed with ethanolic potash (50 ml; 20%) for 4 hr, ethanol recovered and the residue acidified with hydrochloric acid. On working up with ether in normal manner, *pure 2-methyl cyclo-octan-1-one* had b.p. $71^\circ-2^\circ/3.5$ mm. (Yield : 0.58 g; 62%).

Its semicarbazone had m.p. $127^\circ-8^\circ$ (Lit. $127^\circ-8^\circ$). The other products were similarly obtained and are entered in the following tables.

TABLE I

Ethyl 2-alkyl/arylalkyl cyclo-octan-1-one-2-carboxylate (II)

S.No.	R	B.P. °C	Ref.	Index	Yield %	Formula	Found %		Requires %	
							C	H	C	H
1.	Ethyl	141-3/14 mm	n_D^{21}	1.4691	64.7	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3$	64.5	9.8	64.6	9.7
2.	Allyl	158-60/14mm	n_D^{28}	1.4765	58.3	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3$	70.5	9.2	70.6	9.2
3.	Benzyl	164-5/2 mm	n_D^{21}	1.5201	71.0	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_3$	75.0	8.2	75.0	8.3

TABLE 2

Ethyl 2-alkyl/arylalkylcyclo-octan-1-one-2-glyoxalate

S. No.	Alkyl/ Arylalkyl	B.P. °C	Ref.	Index	Yield %	Formula	Found %		Requires %	
							C	H	C	H
1.	Ethyl	107-8/3mm	n_D^{21}	1.4651	72.0	$C_{14}H_{22}O_4$	66.0	8.6	66.1	8.7
2.	Allyl	121-3/1mm	—	—	75.0	$C_{15}H_{22}O_4$	67.6	8.4	67.6	8.3
3.	Benzyl	165-7/1mm	n_D^{21}	1.5188	69.5	$C_{16}H_{24}O_4$	72.0	7.5	72.1	7.6

TABLE 3

2-Alkyl/Aryl alkyl cyclo-octa-1-one (III)

S.No.	R	B.P. °C	Ref.	Index	Yield %	Formula	Found%		Requires%		2:4- DNP °C	Semi- carba- zone °C
							C	H	C	H		
1.	Ethyl	84-6/5 mm	n_D^{26}	1.4828	66.0	$C_{10}H_{16}O$	78.0	11.8	77.9	11.7	95	133
2.	Allyl	122-3/14mm	n_D^{26}	1.4778	75.0	$C_{11}H_{16}O$	79.3	11.0	79.5	10.8	96	132
3.	Benzyl	141-2/2 mm	n_D^{26}	1.5268	66.0	$C_{15}H_{20}O$	83.2	9.3	83.3	9.3	117	—

The ketone No. 1 on Clemmensen reduction gave ethyl cyclo-octane b.p. 108-110°/1mm in 50% yield. n_D^{21} 1.4658. (Found : C, 85.5; H, 14.1. $C_{10}H_{20}O$ requires C, 85.7; H, 14.3%).

Cis-2-Benzyl cyclo-octan-1-ol : To a solution of 2-benzylcyclo-octan-1-one (1.1 g; 0.005 mol) in absolute ethanol (40 ml), contained in a R.B. flask fitted with a reflux condenser carrying a guard tube, was added sodium borohydride (0.76 g; 0.02 mol) and the reaction mixture after refluxing for 2 hrs was kept overnight. The contents were later poured into water, acidified with dil. hydrochloric acid, extracted with ether and the ethereal solution on working up in the customary manner gave pure *cis-2-benzylcyclo-octan-1-ol* at 163°-4°/3.5 mm. (Yield : 0.7 g; 70%). n_D^{26} 1.5351. (Found : C, 82.4; H, 10.2. $C_{15}H_{22}O$ requires C, 82.6; H, 10.1%).

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